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Impact of Heuristic Teaching Method on Student Achievement in Geometry at the Secondary School Level

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the effect of heuristic teaching technique on the academic achievement of secondary school students in geometry concepts. This study specifically adopted quasi experimental research design. The population of the study comprised of 952 SS 2 students in two government owned secondary schools in Itesiwaju Local Government Area of Oyo State. The sample of the study comprised 120 SS 2 students. Multi stage sampling technique was used to select the study sample. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The instruments used for the study were Heuristic Learning Strategy (HLS) and Geometry Achievement Test (GAT). The instrument was validated and the reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined using Richard-Kuderson 20 (kR_{20}) as 0.82. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that heuristic learning strategy enhanced students' achievement in Geometry Concepts and that gender is a significant factor in students' achievement in geometry. The study recommended that: heuristic learning strategy should be used in teaching students to improve their achievement in geometry concepts and mathematics in general. School administrators should organize seminar and workshops to equip teachers on the processes of utilizing heuristic teaching strategy for teaching and government should furnish schools with needed facility that could enhance the use of HTT in teaching geometry concepts and mathematics.

Keywords: Geometry Concepts, Senior Secondary Schools, Students Achievement, Heuristic Teaching Technique, Learning

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is a way of describing relationships between number and other measurable quantities. Azuka (2013) sees Mathematics as not only the language of the science, it is essential nutrient for thought, logic, reasoning and therefore, progress. Mathematics is a crucial discipline that facilitates the scientific and technical advancement of a nation. Mathematics is an essential and compulsory subject for pupils in Basic Education and Secondary School (FRN, 2017) Some branches of Mathematics are characterized by use of strict proofs based on axioms. Some of its major sub-divisions are arithmetic, algebra, geometry, trigonometry and calculus. Usman (2002) stated that mathematics is one of the most powerful and adaptable mental tools which the intelligence of man has made for its own use, collectively over the centuries.

Mathematics according to Kolawole and Ajetunmobi (2013) is an instrument to facilitate the learning of other formal school's subject, and also very vital tool for resolving problem situation in all disciplines. Roohi (2015) opined that ignoring knowledge of mathematics detrimentally affects all discipline, since one is uninformed in this discipline cannot comprehend other sciences or worldly matters. The advancement of both national and human development is predominantly reliant on the progress of science and technology, with mathematics serving as foundation (Haruna,2014).

Though Mathematics is very important and compulsory for every citizen of worth in the nation, students' performance in mathematics in the nation (in both internal and external examinations) have remained consistently poor and unsatisfied (Nwadiae, 2010). This unimaginable level of poor performance in Mathematics across all level of educational echelon has continued to be an issue of immense concern to stakeholders in education enterprise including educational administrators, researchers, teachers and parents. As such, a pragmatic and conscientious proactive decision and action ought to be taken by concerned stakeholders to checkmate these incidents of mass failure in Mathematics, so as to save nation from imminent collapse of her educational sector (Kolawole, 2013).

The achievement of students in mathematics has been a significant worry in society. Academic achievement refers to the level of success a student attains in any assessment or examination following a teaching method or programme. There are ample evidences of continued poor performance of students in both standardized and teacher's made examinations (Agwagha & Benjamin, 2006). There has been an increasing mass failure in mathematics as a subject in most external examinations such as West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council of Nigeria (NECO) (Chief Examination Report, 2015).

The national mathematics curriculum for secondary schools categorizes mathematics into 5 sections: number and numeration, algebraic processes, geometry, statistics and probability. The Chief Examiner's report revealed that the percentages of students who fail in obtaining a credit pass in Mathematics at the senior secondary certificate Examination was due to their poor attempt at all trigonometric and geometric relation questions. Some studies have investigated the major factors which constitute problems to the achievement of secondary schools' students in mathematics among them include, students negative attitude towards mathematics (Ukpebor, 2005).

Challenged by the problem of improving students' performance in Mathematical knowledge and skills, researchers and Mathematics educators have suggested various new teaching methods. For instance, Iji (2003) suggested cooperative and individual teaching and learning strategies. Research by Nwafor, Okpala, and Okoi (2019) demonstrated that heuristic technique enhances students' academic achievement compared to conventional teaching method. Heuristic learning strategy is a problem-solving approach that involves using mental shortcuts, trial and error, and exploration to find solutions.

Heuristics learning strategy develops problem-solving skills of students, enhances critical thinking, and builds confidence and persistence of students. It involves guess and check to find solutions to algebraic equations or geometry problems. The guided heuristic teaching technique is characterized by problem solving, critical thinking, reflective heuristics, and deductive reasoning, rather than just personal assumptions. It is a pedagogical approach that encompasses probing, inquiry investigation, analysis, synthesis, discovery, evaluation, questioning, and critical thinking (Adejo, 2015).

Another significant aspect in this study is the gender of mathematics students. Various definitions of gender exist in research literature. According to Musimenta, Akena, (2020), gender is the social construction of various physical, biological, mental, and behavioral features linked to male and female sex differences. It is the social and cultural creation of roles, access to, and control over resources in society between men and women, or boys and girls (Chilisa & Ntseane, 2010; Fogliati & Bussey 2013). In any given social context, gender characterizes the differences in social roles, responsibilities, constraints, opportunities, and needs of females and males (Akena, 2020). Hence, gender refers to the cultural constructs and social positions which members of the society attach to being male and female. Imoko (2015) found no significant difference in terms of retention between male and female students

while some researchers discovered a significant difference in the mean retention scores of female and male students.

The inconsistencies in these findings have continued to attract the attention of researchers which ought to continue to determine if gender differences exist in students' achievement in mathematics especially when taught using heuristics teaching technique. It is based on these reasons that the present study examined the effect of heuristics teaching technique on the academic achievement of secondary school students in geometry concepts.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study.

1. What are the mean achievement scores of secondary school students taught geometry concepts using heuristic teaching technique and those taught using conventional lecture method?
2. What is the influence of gender on mean achievement scores of secondary schools students' taught geometry concepts using heuristic teaching technique and those taught using conventional lecture method?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

HO₁ There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of secondary school students taught geometry concepts using heuristic teaching technique and those taught using conventional lecture method?

HO₂: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female secondary school students in geometry concepts using heuristic teaching technique and those taught using conventional lecture method?

METHODS

The study adopted a pretest posttest non-equivalent control group quasi-experimental design. Intact classes were used and a pretest was administered before treatment, then a posttest after treatments. The treatment sessions for both experimental group and control lasted for 6 weeks. The experimental group was exposed to geometry concepts through heuristics learning technique while the control group was exposed to geometry concepts learning through conventional lecture method.

Two government owned secondary schools were selected purposefully from the eleven government owned secondary schools in Itesiwaju Local government area of Oyo state, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of 952 female and 610 male) senior secondary school 2 students in the eleven-government owned secondary schools in Itesiwaju Local Government Area of Oyo state. The sample size comprised of 120 (62 female and 58 male) SS 2 students. The sample size was drawn using multistage sampling procedure. Purposeful sampling technique was to draw two secondary schools out of eleven. The criteria for selecting two secondary schools were that the schools must be in existence for at least period of ten years ago with government employed mathematics teacher. Based on this Okaka Grammar School and Baptist Grammar School, Otu were selected. Random sampling was used to assigned the selected schools to experimental and control groups by tossing of a coin and purposeful sampling technique was used to select Department of Art from the selected schools based on the department that usually had high failure rate in mathematics.

Two main instruments were used in this study; treatment instrument (Heuristic learning strategy) and 30 multiple items of Geometry Achievement Test (GAT) which covered geometry concepts taught by the teachers. Before embarking on the experiment, the researchers administered pre-test questions to both experimental and the control groups. The experimental group was exposed to geometry concepts lesson using heuristic learning technique for period of six weeks while the control group was taught the same concept using the conventional lecture method.

After the duration of 6 weeks of treatment for the experimental group and the six weeks of lecture method for the control group, the multiple-choice pre-test questions were reshuffled and administered as the post-test (GAT) to both experimental and the control groups. The researchers collected the script, marked and analyzed the scores using frequency counts, mean, standard deviation and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The

GAT was validated by two experts from department of mathematics and measurement, all from Federal College of Education, Eha-Amufu. The reliability estimate of the GAT was established using internal consistency method and applying Kuder-Richardson 20 (kR₂₀). The reliability coefficient was 0.82.

RESULTS

This section deals with the presentation of results. The results are presented in line with the research questions and the hull hypotheses formulated for the study.

Research question One: *What are the mean achievement scores of secondary school students taught geometry concepts using heuristic teaching technique and those taught using conventional lecture method?*

Table 1: The mean and Standard Deviation (SD) achievement scores of Senior Secondary School students taught Geometry Concept using Heuristic Learning Technique (HLT) and those taught using Conventional Lecture Method (CLM)?

Methods	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
HLT	70	22.81	2.18	43.48	8.06	20.67
CLM	50	23.28	1.65	38.64	10.24	15.36
Difference		0.47				

Result in table 1 above shows the mean achievement and standard deviation scores of SS 2 students taught Geometry concepts using heuristic learning technique (HLT) and those taught using conventional learning method (CLM). Result shows that the HLT group had mean achievement score of 22.81 with standard deviation of 2.18 at pretest and mean achievement score of 43.48 with standard deviation of 8.06 at posttest recording a mean gain of 20.67. Furthermore, the group taught Basic Geometry concepts using CLM had mean achievement score of 23.28 with standard deviation of 1.65 at pretest and mean achievement score of 38.64 with standard deviation of 10.24 at posttest recording a mean gain of 15.36. The table also revealed small difference in the mean of the pre-test scores of the two groups of students to be 0.47. Also, the results showed that the pretest standard deviations for the two groups were smaller than the posttest standard deviations. This means that the pretest scores of the respondents were more homogeneous in each case and cluster around the means than the posttest scores. For each of the groups, the posttest mean scores were greater than the pretest mean scores with HLT group having a higher mean gain. This is an indication that SS 2 students taught Basic Geometry concepts using HLT achieved better than those taught Geometry concepts using CLM.

Hypotheses 1

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of secondary school students taught geometry concepts using heuristic teaching technique and those taught using conventional lecture method?

Table 2: Analysis of covariance on the mean achievement scores of SS 2 students taught Geometry Concepts with HLT and CLM

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	2119.360 ^a	4	529.840	7.021	.000	.175
Intercept	2286.299	1	2286.299	30.294	.000	.187
Pretest	40.999	1	40.999	.543	.462	.004
Techniques	397.621	1	397.621	5.269	.003	.038
Gender	1261.870	1	1261.870	16.720	.000	.112
Techniques * Gender	79.905	1	79.905	1.059	.305	.008
Error	9962.070	115	75.470			
Total	244845.000	120				
Corrected Total	12081.431	118				

a. R Squared = .175 (Adjusted R Squared = .150)

Table 2 showed that the F-ratio is 5.269 with 1 degree of freedom and p-value of .003. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected because the exact probability value of .003 is less than the level of significance set at 0.05. Therefore, the researcher concludes that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of SS 2 students taught Geometry Concepts using heuristic learning technique (HLT) and those taught using conventional lecture method (CLM)..

Research Question Two: *What is the influence of gender on mean achievement scores of secondary schools students' taught geometry concepts using heuristic teaching technique and those taught using conventional lecture method?*

Table 3: The mean and Standard Deviation (SD) scores of influence of gender on mean achievement of SS 2 students' in Basic Geometry Concepts.

Gender	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Male	58	23.22	1.68	46.17	4.67	22.95
Female	72	22.96	2.05	39.46	10.06	16.50
Difference		0.26				

Result in Table 3 above shows the mean and standard deviation scores of influence of gender on mean achievement of SS 2 students in Geometry Concepts. Result shows that the male students had mean achievement score of 23.22 with standard deviation of 1.68 at pretest and mean achievement score of 46.17 with standard deviation of 4.67 at posttest recording a mean achievement gain of 22.95. Again, the female students had mean achievement score of 22.96 with standard deviation of 2.05 at pretest and mean achievement score of 39.46 with standard deviation of 10.06 at posttest recording a mean gain of 16.50. The table also revealed small difference in the mean of the pre-test scores of male and female students to be 0.26. This tends to imply that the male and female students appeared to have the same level of knowledge on what they were to learn before the experiments. Also, the results showed that the pretest standard deviations for male and female groups were smaller than the posttest standard deviations. This means that the pretest scores of the respondents were more homogeneous in each case and cluster around the means than the posttest scores. Finally, the posttest mean achievement score for male and female students were greater than the pretest mean scores with male students having a higher mean achievement gain. This is an indication that the male students achieved higher than their female counterparts when taught Geometry Concepts.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female secondary school students in geometry concepts using heuristic teaching technique and those taught using conventional lecture method?

Table 2 shows that the F-ratio is 16.720 with 1 degree of freedom and p-value of 0.000. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected because the exact probability value of 0.000 is less than the level of significance set at 0.05. Therefore, the researcher concludes that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female SS 2 students in Geometry Concepts.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of heuristic teaching technique on the academic achievement of secondary school students in geometry concept. The findings of the study showed that heuristic teaching technique is highly effective in increasing students' achievement score in Geometry concept because students taught using heuristics technique performed better than their counterpart taught using conventional lecture method. Also, the finding of this study also showed that male students demonstrated slightly higher achievement in Geometry concept than their female counterparts.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that heuristic teaching technique has higher positive effect on achievement in Geometry concepts. It was also concluded that gender is a significant factor in students' achievement in basic geometry concepts.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings, the researcher recommended that:

1. Heuristic teaching technique should be used in teaching students to improve their achievement in geometry concept specifically and mathematics in general.
2. School administrators should organize seminar and workshops for training of mathematics teachers on the process of utilization of heuristic teaching technique for learning of mathematics.
3. Government should furnish schools with needed facility that could enhance the use of heuristic teaching technique in teaching mathematics.

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